

ISic0234

I.Sicily inscription 0234

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found in construction material in the old castle

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 66

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) [M(anibus)]
2. M(arcus) Vill[ius---]
3. vix(it) a[nn(is) ---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285290

EDR 127513

EDCS 10900664

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0787

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 160
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 302

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